

Policy Brief:
The Increasing Importance of Occupation-Restricted Immigration

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Abstract

- “Occupation-restricted” immigration policy legally restricts immigrants to certain occupations specified at the point of entry.
- Occupation-restricted immigration policy contrasts with “skill-based” immigration policy, which admits high-skilled immigrants and allows them to work in the occupations of their choosing.
- Skill-based immigration generally lowers the wages of the subset of native workers who compete with immigrants in the labour market.
- In contrast to skill-based immigration policy, a well-designed occupation-restricted immigration policy can raise wages for all native workers regardless of skill.
- Because occupation-restricted immigration is less likely to lower the wages of native workers than skill-based immigration, occupation-restricted immigration is less likely to provoke political backlash. For this reason, I predict that occupation-restricted immigration will become more important relative to skill-based immigration in the coming decades.
- Increasing occupation-restricted immigration is likely to increase the wages of native workers and to improve the fiscal position of the government.
- At the same time, increasing occupation-restricted immigration may increase social tensions by creating a semi-permanent, unassimilated underclass of immigrant workers and may raise difficult questions in ethics, law, and foreign policy. The government should begin to prepare for these possible consequences now.

Main Analysis

Immigration has become one of the most contentious political issues in societies worldwide. Controversy around immigration is driven by two trends. First, birthrates are falling worldwide,

and, as a result, labour forces are aging. As workers age and retire, labour becomes scarce, driving up production costs and prompting firms to search for new sources of labour. In a context of labour scarcity, immigration can increase productivity and output. However, immigration does not generate this effect uniformly. When immigration is unrestricted, immigrant workers compete with at least some subset of native workers, driving down wages for these workers. This effect of immigration drives the second trend, namely that political opposition to immigration is rising worldwide. Opposition to immigration is led by workers who stand to lose the most from immigration.

How can policy makers reconcile increasing economic need for immigration with increasing political backlash against immigration? To date, the UK and other European countries have attempted to square this circle through what I will refer to as skill-based immigration. Skill-based immigration policies prioritize admission of highly skilled immigrants but then allow these immigrants to work in a relatively unrestricted range of occupations. Skill-based immigration may mute political opposition to immigration if high-skilled immigrants compete primarily with high-skilled native workers, and if high-skilled native workers have less political influence (or are less inclined to use this influence) than less-skilled native workers.

The use of skill-based immigration to dampen political opposition to immigration has two problems. First, the assumption that high-skilled native workers are less politically influential than less-skilled native workers may be incorrect. Second, even if the assumption is correct, it is difficult to ensure that immigrants admitted under skill-based policies confine themselves to the high-skilled labour market. If “skilled immigrants” in fact choose to work in less-skill intensive jobs, then these immigrants drive down wages for less-skilled native workers, precisely the outcome that skill-based immigration policies are designed to prevent. An example of this problem in the UK is the controversy over “Deliveroo visas.” This term refers to the idea that immigrants admitted under skill-based policies such as the graduate route visa may in fact choose to work in less skill-intensive jobs such as food delivery.

In this brief, I will describe an immigration policy that is an alternative to skill-based immigration. I will refer to this policy as “occupation-restricted immigration”. Under occupation-restricted immigration, immigrants are legally restricted to certain occupations specified at the time of entry. Immigrants admitted under these policies are not required to demonstrate high skills, and in fact in many cases occupation-restricted immigration policies specifically target relatively low-skilled occupations. An example from the UK is the seasonal worker visa, which allows (temporary) immigration specifically and exclusively for the purposes of working in the horticulture or poultry processing industries. This form of immigration currently makes up a relatively small share of total immigration into the UK.

Unlike skill-based immigration, occupation-restricted immigration has the potential to benefit all native workers regardless of skill. To see why, consider a stylized example of a region that has two industries employing less-skilled workers, poultry processing and fast-food service. It will be important for the analysis that follows that poultry processing and fast-food service are **complements**. What this means is the following. As the supply of workers in the poultry-processing industry goes up, the price of poultry goes down, which means that the price of fast-food falls and so consumption of fast-food increases. As consumption of fast-food increases, demand for fast-food service workers increases. If the number of fast-food service workers is held fixed, then an increase in the number of poultry processing workers causes the wage of fast-food service workers to increase.

Initially, suppose that there are no immigrants and that both poultry-processing and fast-food jobs are held by less-skilled native workers. Now suppose that an immigration reform allows less-skilled immigrant workers to enter, but only to hold poultry-processing jobs. If the number of immigrants is small, native workers continue to hold both kinds of jobs. Since native workers can choose either kind of job, the wages in both industries must be (roughly) the same to induce native workers to enter both industries. Increases in immigration cause some native workers to move out of poultry-processing and into fast-food, but relative wages in the two industries are not affected. The increase in the total supply of less-skilled labour due to immigration then causes the overall wage of less-skilled workers to fall, harming less-skilled native workers. So far, this effect is the same as the effect of unrestricted immigration discussed earlier.

As the number of immigrants increases, however, at some point all native workers leave the poultry-processing industry and enter the fast-food industry. At this point, further increases in immigration start to have different effects. Because there are no native workers in the poultry-processing industry, and because immigrants legally cannot work in the fast-food industry, there is no mechanism leading to the equalization of fast-food and poultry-processing wages. Further increases in immigration lead to further decreases in the poultry-processing wage. However, due to the complementarity between poultry-processing and fast-food, further increases in immigration cause the fast-food wage to **increase**. A sufficiently large increase in immigration can increase the wage of fast-food workers above the level that these workers would obtain without any immigration. Intuitively, the benefits to fast-food workers from an increase in the complementary supply of poultry-processing workers more than make up for the cost to fast-food workers of an overall increase in the supply of less-skilled labour. Thus, occupation-restricted immigration can benefit native workers, even when both native workers and immigrant workers have similar skills.

In the previous example, there are only two occupations, and occupation-restricted immigration can have positive or negative effects on native workers. In reality, there are many occupations. In my paper, “The Economics of Discriminatory Job Reservations”, cited below, I show that with many occupations, a properly designed occupation-restricted immigration policy **always** benefits **all** native workers. Thus, occupation-restricted immigration is less likely to provoke political opposition than skill-based immigration.

Because occupation-restricted migration is likely to generate less political opposition than skill-based migration, I predict that occupation-restricted immigration will become a larger share of overall immigration in the UK and Europe in the coming decades. To understand how this trend may develop in the UK, it is helpful to consider an example of a society that has already implemented large-scale occupation-restricted immigration, namely Japan. Figure 1 below shows the number of foreign residents in Japan by source country. Prior to the 1990s, Japan had almost no foreign residents except for a population of ethnic Koreans who had relocated, often involuntarily, during World War 2. Starting in the 1990s, Japan began to allow increasing levels of immigration. One of the first groups of immigrants consisted of relatively highly skilled, ethnically Japanese workers descended from a previous wave of Japanese emigrants to Brazil. These immigrants were granted unrestricted visas that allowed them to work in any industry. However, these immigrants provoked political opposition and by 2009 the Japanese government was providing incentives for these immigrants to return to Brazil, leading to a decline in this form of immigration.

Figure 1

Source: Japanese Immigration Services Agency, <https://www.moj.go.jp/isa/>

Around the same time as the increase in high-skilled immigration from Brazil, the Japanese government began to allow increasing numbers of less-skilled immigrants, initially from China and then from South-East Asia, especially the Philippines and Vietnam. Most of these immigrants were admitted under one of two immigration schemes, the Technical Intern Training scheme and the Specified Skilled Worker scheme. Under each scheme, workers are allowed to work only in specific occupations. For example, some occupations allowed for Specified Skilled Workers include restaurant services, automobile maintenance, and bus drivers. As these occupational categories suggest, and despite their names, both programs admit relatively low-skilled immigrants.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of foreign residents in Japan by immigration status as of 2024. The categories of “Permanent Resident” and “Study Abroad” do not represent recent immigrants who are part of the labour force, and so these categories can be ignored. The category “Technical/Humanities/International Services” corresponds to skill-based immigration. Members of this category are highly skilled professional workers, often from Europe or the United States. The remaining two categories are the two occupation-restricted immigration schemes. Figure 2 shows that the combined numbers of immigrants in the two occupation-restricted categories are greater than the number of skill-based immigrants.

Figure 2

Status	Number of residents
Permanent Resident	932,090
Technical/Humanities/International Services	458,109
Technical Intern Training scheme	449,432
Study Abroad	435,203
Specified Skilled Worker scheme	336,196

Source: Japanese Immigration Services Agency, <https://www.moj.go.jp/>

As a result of occupation-restricted immigration in Japan, certain occupations such as vegetable-picking and garment manufacture now almost exclusively employ immigrants. The analysis in this brief suggests that this trend has increased wages for both high-skilled and less-skilled native Japanese workers due to the complementarity between jobs held by immigrants and jobs held by native workers. Occupation-restricted migration also generates fiscal resources for the Japanese government, both directly through visa fees paid by immigrants and indirectly through increased tax revenue generated from increased productivity in Japanese firms.

At the same time, however, occupation-restricted immigration has created social tensions in Japanese society. By design, occupation-restricted immigrants receive substantially lower wages than similarly skilled native Japanese workers, and so occupation-restricted immigrants have come to form a semi-permanent underclass in Japanese society with little hope of upward social mobility. The existence of this unassimilated underclass has created social conflict and has caused some observers to raise ethical and legal concerns. Poor conditions and low wages for immigrant workers in Japan have also created diplomatic frictions with immigrant source countries such as Vietnam.

The Japanese experience provides a guide to both possible benefits and possible problems that may appear in the UK if, as I predict, the UK also chooses to increase occupation-restricted immigration in the coming decades. On the one hand, occupation-restricted immigration is likely to deliver unambiguous and broad-based economic benefits for both high-skilled and less-skilled native workers and for the UK government. On the other hand, large-scale occupation-restricted immigration is likely to create a semi-permanent, unassimilated immigrant underclass, which may give rise to various social, ethical, and legal problems. A complete analysis of these potential problems is beyond the scope of my expertise. However, my policy recommendation is that the government should begin to study and prepare for these potential problems now.

Recommended Reading

The analysis in this brief is based on my recent paper, “The Economics of Discriminatory Job Reservations”, forthcoming in the *American Economic Journal: Microeconomics*, available here: <https://www.aeaweb.org/articles?id=10.1257/mic.20250072>. (Open access version available here: <https://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/id/eprint/235307/1/discrimination43.pdf>)

A very useful resource discussing a variety of innovative immigration policies, including many that I would classify as occupation-restricted immigration policies, is the global skill partnerships website, available at <https://gsp.cgdev.org/>. This website contains information on the Japanese Technical Intern Training scheme and the Selective Skilled Worker scheme, as well as other related immigration policies in other countries including many European countries.

A journalistic account of the Japanese immigration experience is here: <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/02/10/business/japan-immigrants-workers-trump.html>

Further Information

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